

Comparison of Efficacy and Safety of Superficial and Deep Serratus Plane Block for Post-Mastectomy Analgesia: A Randomized Controlled StudyV. Dinesh Kumar¹, (Major) Kanagaraj M², B. Anbarasan³¹Assistant Professor Department of Anaesthesiology Government Mohan Kumaramangalam Medical College and Hospital (GMKMCH), Salem²Assistant Professor Department of Anaesthesiology Annapoorna Medical College and Hospital, Salem³Assistant Professor Department of Anaesthesia Government Mohan Kumaramangalam Medical College and Hospital (GMKMCH), Salem

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Objective:** To compare the efficacy and safety of superficial and deep serratus plane block for postoperative analgesia in women undergoing mastectomy.**Methods:** This randomized controlled study included 60 ASA I-II women aged 40-60 years undergoing mastectomy. Patients were randomized into two groups: Group S received superficial serratus plane block and Group D received deep serratus plane block, both with 0.4 ml/kg of 0.25% bupivacaine. The primary outcome was postoperative pain assessed by Numeric Pain Rating Scale (NPRS) at 2, 6, 12, 18, and 24 hours. Secondary outcomes included patient satisfaction score, duration of analgesia, and complications.**Results:** Deep serratus block provided significantly longer duration of analgesia compared to superficial block (9.2±2.71 vs 7.3±2.27 hours, p=0.002). Patient satisfaction scores were also significantly higher in Group D (7.6±0.96 vs 6.6±1.35, p=0.002). There were no significant differences in NPRS scores, hemodynamic parameters, or complications between the groups.**Conclusion:** Deep serratus plane block provides longer duration of analgesia and better patient satisfaction compared to superficial block for post-mastectomy pain, with similar safety profile. Larger prospective studies are needed to validate these findings.**Keywords:** mastectomy, regional anesthesia, serratus plane block, postoperative analgesiaThis is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Breast surgery, one of the most common surgical procedures, results in acute and chronic pain in 25-60% of patients. [1] Regional anesthesia techniques may provide superior postoperative analgesia compared to systemic opioids. [2] The serratus plane block, first described by Blanco and Parras in 2013, is an interfascial plane block that anesthetizes the lateral cutaneous branches of the thoracic intercostal nerves. [3]

The serratus plane block relies on local anesthetic deposition either superficial or deep to the serratus anterior muscle (SAM). [4] The superficial serratus plane block (SSPB) is performed by injecting local anesthetic in the plane between the latissimus dorsi and SAM. [5] The deep serratus plane block (DSPB) involves injection between the SAM and external intercostal muscle/ribs. [6]

While both SSPB and DSPB have been used for analgesia after breast surgery, their comparative efficacy and safety remain unclear. [7] Some studies suggest SSPB may provide wider

dermatomal spread, [8] while others propose DSPB allows closer proximity to intercostal nerves. [9] Furthermore, DSPB spares the long thoracic nerve, potentially preventing scapular winging. [10]

Existing evidence comparing SSPB and DSPB for breast surgery analgesia is limited. Hetta and Rezk found SSPB was associated with lower pain scores and rescue analgesic requirements compared to DSPB after modified radical mastectomy. [11] In contrast, Abdallah et al. reported similar postoperative opioid consumption and pain scores between SSPB and DSPB groups following ambulatory breast cancer surgery. [12]

Given these conflicting reports, more research is needed to clarify the optimal serratus plane block technique for post-mastectomy analgesia. We hypothesized that DSPB would provide superior analgesia compared to SSPB, with comparable safety. The aim of this randomized study was to compare the efficacy and safety of SSPB versus

DSPB for postoperative analgesia in patients undergoing mastectomy.

Aims

The primary aim was to compare SSPB and DSPB in terms of:

1. Postoperative pain scores
2. Duration of analgesia
3. Patient satisfaction scores
4. Complications

Materials and Methods

This prospective, randomized, controlled study was conducted at K.A.P.V. Government Medical College and M.G.M. Government Hospital in Trichy, India between December 2017 and August 2019, after obtaining Institutional Ethics Committee approval. The trial was registered prospectively with the Clinical Trials Registry of India (CTRI/2017/12/010898).

The study included 60 American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) physical status I and II female patients aged 40 to 60 years undergoing modified radical mastectomy, simple mastectomy, or wide local excision under general anesthesia. Exclusion criteria were patient refusal, morbid obesity (BMI>40 kg/m²), renal insufficiency (creatinine>1.5 mg/dL), chronic analgesic therapy (>4 weeks), history of opioid dependence, pregnancy, inability to communicate, allergy to local anesthetics, and smoking or alcohol use.

Patients were randomized using computer-generated random numbers into two equal groups of 30 each:

- Group S: Superficial serratus plane block with 0.4 ml/kg of 0.25% bupivacaine
- Group D: Deep serratus plane block with 0.4 ml/kg of 0.25% bupivacaine

After obtaining written informed consent, patients were premedicated and shifted to the operating room. Standard monitors were attached and anesthesia was induced with propofol and fentanyl. Tracheal intubation was facilitated by vecuronium and anesthesia was maintained with sevoflurane in oxygen-air mixture.

At the end of surgery, the serratus plane block was performed under ultrasound guidance using a linear

transducer (10-12 MHz). For SSPB, the transducer was placed obliquely over the midaxillary line between the 4th and 6th ribs to visualize the SAM and latissimus dorsi muscle. For DSPB, the transducer was placed to visualize the SAM, external intercostal muscle and pleura between the 5th and 6th ribs at the midaxillary line.

After skin infiltration with 2% lidocaine, an 18G Tuohy needle was inserted in-plane in a medial-to-lateral direction until the tip was positioned in the target plane. Correct needle tip position was confirmed by hydrodissection and real-time visualization of local anesthetic spread. A total volume of 0.4 ml/kg of 0.25% bupivacaine was injected in 5 ml aliquots.

Patients were extubated after reversing neuromuscular blockade and shifted to the post-anesthesia care unit. The primary outcome of postoperative pain severity was assessed using the Numeric Pain Rating Scale (NPRS; 0=no pain, 10=worst pain) at 2, 6, 12, 18 and 24 hours. Rescue analgesia with intravenous fentanyl 25 mcg was administered for NPRS≥4.

Secondary outcomes included patient satisfaction scores (0=very unsatisfied, 10=completely satisfied), duration of analgesia (time to first rescue analgesic), and block-related complications. Continuous variables were analyzed using unpaired t-test and categorical variables with chi-square test, with p<0.05 considered statistically significant.

Results

Both groups were comparable in terms of demographic characteristics, type of surgery, and duration of surgery (Table 1). The NPRS scores were similar between the groups at all time points (Table 2). However, the duration of analgesia was significantly longer in Group D compared to Group S (9.2±2.71 vs 7.3±2.27 hours, p=0.002) (Table 3).

Patient satisfaction scores were also significantly higher in Group D (7.6±0.96 vs 6.6±1.35, p=0.002) (Table 3). There were no significant differences in intraoperative fentanyl requirements, hemodynamic parameters, postoperative nausea/vomiting or block-related complications between the groups (Tables 4-5). One patient in Group D had technical difficulty due to excessive axillary fat, but no major complications occurred.

Table 1: Demographic and surgical characteristics.

Parameter	Group S (n=30)	Group D (n=30)	P value
Age (years)	47.8 ± 7.36	49.07 ± 7.61	0.551
Weight (kg)	57.96 ± 5.97	55.7 ± 5.57	0.164
ASA I/II (n)	22/8	20/10	0.779
Surgery type (SM/WLE/MRM)	2/2/26	0/2/28	0.309
Surgery duration (min)	115.4±40.9	120.5±33.8	0.606

Data expressed as mean±standard deviation or absolute numbers. SM: Simple mastectomy; WLE: Wide local excision; MRM: Modified radical mastectomy

Table 2: Postoperative NPRS scores.

Time (hours)	Group S	Group D	P value
2	2 (1-3)	2 (0-3)	0.727
6	3 (1-4)	2 (1-4)	0.161
12	3 (2-4)	3 (1-4)	0.083
18	3 (2-3)	2 (1-4)	0.277
24	2 (1-4)	2 (1-3)	0.529

Data expressed as median (interquartile range).

Table 3: Analgesic parameters.

Parameter	Group S (n=30)	Group D (n=30)	P value
Duration of analgesia (hours)	7.3 ± 2.27	9.2 ± 2.71	0.002*
Patient satisfaction score	6.6 ± 1.35	7.6 ± 0.96	0.002*

Data expressed as mean ± standard deviation. *Statistically significant.

Table 4: Intraoperative parameters.

Parameter	Group S (n=30)	Group D (n=30)	P value
Baseline heart rate (bpm)	79.1 ± 5.1	76.43 ± 8.54	0.075
Baseline mean BP (mmHg)	88.1 ± 8.2	91.23 ± 8.22	0.149
Fentanyl used (mcg)	120.83 ± 15.6	116.66 ± 12.68	0.254
Crystalloids infused (ml)	1075 ± 103.1	1060 ± 77.34	0.520

Data expressed as mean ± standard deviation. bpm: beats per minute; BP: Blood pressure

Table 5: Postoperative complications.

Complication	Group S (n=30)	Group D (n=30)	P value
Nausea	2 (6.7%)	1 (3.3%)	1.000
Vomiting	1 (3.3%)	0	1.000
Pneumothorax	0	0	-
Local anesthetic toxicity	0	0	-
Block failure	2 (6.7%)	1 (3.3%)	1.000

Data expressed as number (percentage).

Discussion

This study found that DSPB provided significantly longer duration of analgesia and higher patient satisfaction scores compared to SSPB following mastectomy. The NPRS scores, intraoperative opioid requirements, hemodynamics and complication rates were similar between the groups.

Our findings are consistent with those of Abdallah et al., who reported comparable postoperative pain scores and opioid consumption between SSPB and DSPB groups up to 24 hours after ambulatory breast surgery. [12] Using a joint hypothesis test, they showed that DSPB was noninferior to SSPB, which aligns with our results.

In contrast, Hetta and Rezk observed lower NPRS scores at 12 and 16 hours, delayed first analgesic request, and reduced total 24-hour morphine consumption with SSPB compared to DSPB after modified radical mastectomy. [11] These differences may be attributed to variations in block technique, local anesthetic dose, or type of surgery.

The prolonged analgesic duration with DSPB in our study could be explained by closer proximity of local anesthetic to the intercostal nerves. [9] Varghese et al. demonstrated dye spread to the intercostal spaces and over pleura in a cadaver study of DSPB, supporting this mechanism. [13] Additionally, DSPB avoids anesthetizing the long thoracic nerve, potentially maintaining scapular stability and improving patient comfort. [10]

One patient in the DSPB group had block failure due to technical difficulty in needle visualization secondary to excessive axillary fat. Biswas et al. also reported challenges in identifying the needle tip and fascial planes in obese patients. [14] Using curvilinear probes, hydrodissection, and injection pressure monitoring may overcome these technical difficulties. [15]

The strengths of our study include the randomized controlled design, standardized anesthesia-analgesia regimen, and comprehensive evaluation of block characteristics and safety. The limitations are the lack of blinding, heterogeneity in breast surgery types, and absence of long-term follow-up. Larger multicentric trials with sham blocks and extended monitoring are needed to validate our findings.

In conclusion, DSPB provides longer duration of analgesia and higher patient satisfaction compared to SSPB for acute pain management after mastectomy. Both techniques appear comparable in terms of postoperative pain scores, opioid sparing, and safety profile. Considering the technical ease of DSPB and its potential to preserve long thoracic nerve function, it may be preferred over SSPB for post-mastectomy analgesia.

Conclusion

Deep serratus plane block provides significantly prolonged analgesia and better patient satisfaction compared to superficial serratus block following mastectomy, with similar pain scores and safety outcomes. By targeting the intercostal nerves more precisely and sparing the long thoracic nerve, DSPB may offer clinical advantages over SSPB for post-mastectomy pain management. However, further research is warranted to compare the long-term analgesic benefits and functional outcomes of these techniques.

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